

MICROSTRUCTURAL STUDY OF THE SINTERED COMPOSITE COMPOSED OF TIN AND NI

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SUMMARY: Pure TiN powder was mixed with pure Ni powder at a volume ratio of 1:1. Then, the mixed powder was cold compacted. The compacts were pressureless sintered at 1150, 1250 and 1350 °C respectively for 1 hour in vacuum. X-ray diffraction analysis and microstructural analysis by SEM and EDX were carried out with the sintered samples. It is shown that the lattice constant of Ni increases with increasing sintering temperature, but the crystal structure of TiN is stable under the experimental conditions. The Ti content of the Ni solid solution determined from the lattice constant value is very close to the one obtained by EDX quantitative analysis. The experimental results indicate that interdiffusion takes place at the TiN/Ni interface during sintering.

KEYWORDS: ceramic matrix composite, cermet, interface

INTRODUCTION

Various kinds of cermets are widely employed in industry due to their favorable properties which are different from those of ceramics and metals. As one of their representatives, the cermet composed of WC and Co has been used as a wear-resistant material for several decades. However, this cermet is expensive because both tungsten and cobalt are not abundant materials. Furthermore, the high specific gravity of this material makes the parts too heavy to use in some cases especially for aeronautical and astronautical applications. Hence, during the last 30 years many attempts have been made to find alternatives with low specific gravity and relatively comparable mechanical properties coupled with favorable cost [1-9]. Although much significant progress has been reported [1-9], the cermet composed of WC and Co has not been replaced in industry so far. Nevertheless, the effort to look for the alternatives has not stopped.

As reported in Ref. 10-12, in order to achieve this goal, Al₂O₃ and Ni were selected as the starting materials due to their favorable properties and easy availability. However, the problem associated with these two components is the poor wettability between solid Al₂O₃ and liquid Ni [13], which hinders the manufacturing of this cermet by liquid phase sintering. In order to improve the sintering ability of this material, attention was focused on introducing interlayers which could adhere strongly to both the ceramic phase and the metallic phase. It is

reported that TiN was found to be the best suited to achieve this goal. The TiN interlayer was introduced by coating the Al₂O₃ powder with a layer of TiN using CVD process. Then, Al₂O₃ powder coated with TiN (denoted by Al₂O₃-TiN) was mixed with Ni powder. The mixture was hot-pressed to manufacture the composite, which is expressed by Al₂O₃-TiN+Ni [10-12].

In order to investigate the mechanism that TiN interlayer remarkably enhances the sintering ability and mechanical properties of the material, it is essential to study the two interfaces (TiN/Ni and Al₂O₃/TiN) involved in this system. This paper deals with the TiN/Ni interface.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Pure TiN powder (particle size: 5-25 μ m, purity: 99.9 Wt%) was mixed with pure Ni powder (particle size: 1-3 μ m, purity: 99.9 Wt%) at a volume ratio of 1:1 for 45 minutes using a powder mill. The powder was loaded in a plastic cylindrical vessel containing TiN balls 10 mm in diameter for mixing. The mixed powder, 1 gram for each sample, was cold compacted at 750 MPa for 60 seconds. Neither lubricant nor binder was used during compacting. The compacts were pressureless sintered at 1150, 1250 and 1350 °C respectively for 1 hour in vacuum of 7×10^{-3} Pa (5×10^{-5} Torr). After sintering for the required duration, the samples were left in the furnace in vacuum to cool gradually to room temperature.

The sintered billets were ground lightly with 1000 mesh sand paper to remove the surface layer. Then, they were washed in alcohol using an ultrasonic bath. After drying, X-ray diffraction was carried out on all these samples. The polished sections were observed by SEM and the composition of the various phases at the sections was analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively by EDX (Energy Dispersive X-ray Microanalysis System).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows the X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples sintered at the various temperatures. For comparison, the X-ray diffraction pattern of the compact with the same composition is also included in the figure. This figure indicates that with increasing sintering temperature every diffraction peak of Ni shifts to the left side of the figure (low angle), whereas, the diffraction peaks of TiN do not shift. So, according to Bragg's law, the lattice constant a of Ni increases with increasing sintering temperature. Its value as a function of sintering temperature is presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1: X-ray diffraction patterns of the cermet composed of 50 Vol% TiN + 50 Vol% Ni before and after pressureless sintering at various temperatures in vacuum for 1 hour

Fig. 1: Continuing

Fig. 2: Lattice constant a of the Ni solid solution as a function of sintering temperature (For pure Ni: $a=3.5238\text{\AA}$)

A conceivable explanation for the expansion is that dissociation of TiN takes place during sintering [14] resulting in the formation of Ti atoms (or Ti ions), then the Ti atoms diffuse into Ni lattices leading to the expansion, as the atomic radius of Ti (2.00 \AA) is larger than that of Ni (1.62 \AA). The higher the sintering temperature, the more Ti atoms diffuse into Ni lattices, consequently, the larger the lattice constant value will be. Fig. 1 also shows that there is no diffraction peak broadening meaning that the Ni solid solution is homogeneous, which is not surprising for the high temperatures and long duration of sintering applied and the small particle size of Ni.

The quantitative relationship between the lattice constant of Ni solid solution and its Ti content is given in Fig. 3 [15]. Using this figure the Ti content of the Ni solid solutions can be obtained as illustrated in Fig. 4, which shows the Ti content as a function of sintering temperature acquired from the data presented in Fig. 2. From Fig. 4, one can see that the amount of Ti diffused into Ni lattices is significant.

Fig. 5 shows the scanning electron micrographs of the cermet pressureless sintered at $1350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour. Two phases are visible in the micrographs. Various areas from each phase were analyzed by EDX. A representative EDX spectrum for the metallic phase corresponding to the area indicated by the arrow in Fig. 5A is presented in Fig. 6. This figure confirms that the metallic phase consists of Ni and Ti. The quantitative EDX analysis gives the Ti content as $11.1 \pm 0.1\text{ At\%}$ (The uncertain range is standard deviation). This value is very close to the one given in Fig. 4. A representative EDX spectrum for the ceramic phase corresponding to the area indicated by the arrow in Fig. 5B is presented in Fig. 7. This figure indicates that the ceramic phase consists of Ti, N and a small amount of Ni as well. Quantitative EDX analysis shows that the Ni content is below 6 At\% .

Fig. 3: Lattice constant *a* of the Ni solid solution as a function of Ti content

Fig. 4: Ti content of the Ni solid solution as a function of sintering temperature

Fig. 5: Scanning electron micrographs of the cermet composed of 50 Vol% TiN + 50 Vol% Ni pressureless sintered at 1350 °C in vacuum for 1 hour. The metallic phase (A) and the ceramic phase (B) were analyzed by EDX

Fig. 6: EDX spectrum analyzed at the metallic phase as indicated by the arrow in Fig. 5A

Fig. 7: EDX spectrum analyzed at the ceramic phase as indicated by the arrow in Fig. 5B

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the aforementioned experimental results, it can be concluded that during sintering of the compacts composed of 50 Vol% TiN + 50 Vol% Ni at 1150-1350 °C in vacuum for 1 hour, Ti atoms diffuse into Ni lattices forming homogeneous solid solution. This leads to the expansion of the lattice constant. The higher the sintering temperature, the more Ti atoms dissolve, and the more obvious expansion occurs. Only a small amount of Ni diffuses into TiN and dissolves in it. The amount of the Ni is so small that the X-ray diffraction patterns show a stable crystal structure of TiN within the temperature range tested.

It is believed that this interdiffusion also takes place at the TiN/Ni interface involved in the Al₂O₃-TiN+Ni system. For the hot-pressed cermet Al₂O₃-TiN+Ni, this interdiffusion is beneficial to the adhesion at the TiN/Ni interface. Therefore, it can be an explanation of the mechanism that TiN interlayer remarkably enhances the sintering ability and mechanical properties of the Al₂O₃-TiN+Ni system.

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